

Electromagnetic and RF Pulse Design Simulation Based Optimisation of an Eight- Channel Loop Array for 11.7 T Brain Imaging

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Abstract

Purpose: Optimisation of transmit array performance is crucial in ultra-high-field MRI scanners such as 11.7 T due to the increased radiofrequency (RF) losses and RF nonuniformity. This work presents a new workflow to investigate and minimise RF coil losses, and to choose the optimum coil configuration for imaging.

Methods: An 8-channel transceiver loop-array was simulated to analyse its loss mechanism at 499.415 MHz. A folded-end RF shield was developed to limit radiation loss and improve the B_1^+ efficiency. The coil element length, and the shield diameter and length were further optimised using electromagnetic (EM) simulations. The generated EM fields were utilised to perform RF pulse design (RFPD) simulations under realistic constraints. The chosen coil design was constructed to demonstrate performance equivalence in bench and scanner measurements.

Results: The use of conventional RF shields at 11.7 T resulted in significantly high radiation losses of 18.4%. Folding the ends of the RF shield combined with optimising the shield diameter and length increased the absorbed power in biological tissue and reduced the radiation loss to 2.4%. The peak B_1^+ of the optimal array was 42% more than the reference array. Phantom measurements validated the numerical simulations with a close match of within 4% of the predicted B_1^+ .

Conclusion: A workflow, which combines EM and RFPD simulations, to numerically optimise transmit arrays was developed. Results have been validated using phantom measurements. Our findings demonstrate the need for optimizing the RF shield in conjunction with array element design to achieve efficient excitation at 11.7 T.

Keywords: Transmit array design, 11.7 T MRI, parallel transmit, UHF MRI,

1. Introduction

The magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) community has been continuously pushing for higher static magnetic fields with an aim to image the cortical layers and columnar structures at sub-millimetre scale. The promise of a supra-linear boost in signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR), which enables higher resolution imaging as well as unique imaging contrasts, is driving the development of MRI at ultra-high field (UHF) strengths, such as 7 Tesla (T) and beyond.¹⁻⁸ Due to the advances in hardware and MRI methods development, 7T scanners have achieved regulatory approval as a medical device for limited applications.⁹⁻¹⁰ To date, stronger magnets such as 9.4 T and 10.5 T are being used in neuroscience and clinical research.¹¹⁻¹³ Following the trend in increasing static magnetic field strength, a whole-body 11.7T scanner is now operational at CEA, Neurospin, Saclay.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ Further 10.5T and 11.7T scanners are being planned¹⁷ and even a 14T human MRI scanner is currently under consideration¹⁸.

However, there are significant challenges associated with UHF MRI such as inhomogeneous B_1^+ field, increased radiofrequency (RF) power deposition,^{1,4} and increase in magnetic susceptibility and other imaging artifacts.^{1,4,6,19} Because of the increase in magnetic field strength, the Larmor frequency increases and the RF wavelength in tissue becomes shorter than the dimension of the object to be imaged.²⁰ Especially at 11.7 T, the corresponding wavelength in average brain tissue is approximately 7 cm, which is about one-third of the largest dimension of the human head.

The RF power applied to the transmit coil deposits energy in the biological tissue, and this increases with field strength.⁴ Because of the short wavelength, the interactions between the tissue and the electromagnetic (EM) field results in a spatially dependent energy deposition, which increases the potential for localised RF heating.²¹ The energy deposition during routine exams is controlled by the specific absorption rate (SAR) limits, which is a measure of the RF power absorbed per unit mass. Therefore, the ability to provide an efficient and homogeneous RF excitation while operating within the SAR constraints is one of the most important engineering requirements in designing RF transmit coils for UHF MRI.

Transmit arrays are a well-established tool in mitigating the B_1^+ field inhomogeneities at UHF because they offer additional degrees of freedom to manipulate the amplitude and phase of the currents fed to each individual coil element.²²⁻²⁷ The performance of transmit arrays is often assessed in terms of transmit efficiency (B_1^+/\sqrt{P}), safety excitation efficiency (SEE; $B_1^+/\sqrt{\text{SAR}_{10g(\text{max})}}$), and coupling between the coil elements.²²⁻²⁴ Because of the high operating frequency at 11.7 T (499.415 MHz), the Ohmic losses in discrete components are significantly higher in addition to the losses in biological tissue. Practical considerations include the cable loss between the coil input and the RF power amplifier, which can be as high as 3 dB or even more, and limited output power levels from the amplifiers.

In addition, coil configuration also plays an important role in designing transmit arrays. Typically, transmit arrays can be categorised into two groups, namely transceiver (TxRx) arrays^{25,27} and transmit-only receive-only (ToRo) arrays.^{22,24,28} The latter is used most, especially for imaging the brain, because the number of receive channels is not limited by the number of transmit channels. High-density receive arrays have been shown to be beneficial particularly due to their enhanced parallel imaging performance at UHF.²⁹⁻³⁰ However, to accommodate the receive array, the transmit array in ToRo configuration must be constructed on a larger coil housing (typical dimensions for head coils range from 280 to

300 mm diameter tubes), which can further reduce transmit efficiency because the transmit elements are further away from the sample.

Thus, optimising the array design and extracting every performance out of the transmit array is an essential requirement for UHF MRI. In this work, we have developed a proof-of-concept 8-channel transceiver array for imaging at 11.7 T. The design optimisation workflow combines 3D EM and RF pulse design (RFPD) simulations to achieve efficient excitation within SAR constraints. The design process involved extensive numerical simulations to analyse and minimise various loss mechanisms, optimising the coil design in conjunction with the RF shield design, and using the EM fields in RFPD simulations to select the optimal array. The chosen array has been constructed and phantom results as well as ex-vivo brain images are presented in this article. In this proof-of-concept work, an 8-channel transmit array was considered and the dimensions of the RF shield as well as the coil length were varied. Future work will involve 16-channel dual-row designs as they have been shown to enhance parallel transmit (pTx) performance at UHF³¹.

2. Methods

2.1. Optimisation Workflow

In this work, we adopted a new workflow for designing transmit arrays, which combines EM simulations along with RFPD simulations. Firstly, a detailed numerical model of the coil was created in the EM simulation tool – CST Studio Suite 2021 (Dassault Systems, France). To identify all sources of losses within the array, the power budget was investigated. The next step included optimising the coil design to minimise RF losses and hence, increase the power delivered to the biological tissue. This could result in different coil configurations exhibiting similar transmit efficiency. To determine the optimal array for imaging, the workflow included RFPD simulations which were performed under realistic SAR and power constraints and consisted of safety factors for the predictions to be close to the use-case scenario. The chosen array was then constructed, and the simulation results were validated using phantom scans.

2.2. Coil model

A detailed model of the transmit array was created in CST, and simulations were performed using its time-domain solver, which uses finite-integration techniques together with RF circuit co-simulation.³²⁻³³ The coil design consisted of eight identical rectangular loops arranged on a fiberglass tube with 285-mm inner diameter ($\epsilon_r = 5.5$, $\tan \delta = 0.04$, wall thickness 2.5 mm). This diameter was chosen to allow space for a receive-only array. In the numerical domain, the loops were made of 2-mm perfect electric conductor (PEC) wires. Each loop was segmented to accommodate a total of 14 evenly distributed capacitors (13 fixed capacitors and one trimmer) to tune the loops to 499.415 MHz, which corresponds to a segment length of $\lambda/15$. This was empirically determined to ensure that the coil tuning is not dominated by the capacitive coupling to the sample.³⁴ The array elements were matched to 50 Ω through a balanced matching circuit.³⁵ The equivalent circuit is shown in Figure 1A. The fixed capacitors were represented by lumped elements (blue) while the matching circuit and variable capacitors were substituted by 50- Ω discrete ports (red), as shown in Figure 1B. Fixed capacitors were modelled with an equivalent series resistance of 0.438 Ω and an equivalent series inductance of 1.24 nH, which corresponds to 2.4pF 100C-series capacitors (American Technical Ceramics, USA) at 500 MHz. While 100C-series capacitors were chosen due to component availability, it is possible to further reduce the Ohmic loss by selecting lower loss component, for example 800C-series. The variable capacitors (two per channel) were simulated as ideal

capacitors. The transmit array elements were tuned and matched to the Duke body model from the virtual family,³⁶ which had a 2-mm isotropic resolution and was truncated below the shoulder level. Variable capacitors for tuning and matching were adjusted in circuit co-simulations to achieve an impedance match of better than -40 dB for each channel.

The array was decoupled by geometrically overlapping adjacent elements until minimum transmission coefficient (S_{21}) value was reached. The scanner bore was represented by a copper RF shield of 640-mm diameter and 1500 mm in length. The initial model also consisted of a 300-mm long cylindrical RF shield with a diameter of 350 mm. All losses between the coil input and the scanner coil plug such as cable loss and TR switch loss were measured at 499.415 MHz and modelled as an attenuator in circuit co-simulation. Individual B_1^+ field maps were combined by using the linearity superposition principle. To obtain the circularly polarised (CP) mode, an equal power of 1 Watt (W) was applied to all channels with an incremental phase offset of 45°. The power budget and B_1^+ field maps were then obtained using post-processing options available in CST for CP mode excitation.

To ensure that all ports and lumped elements were connected properly, local mesh refinement with a step width of 0.7 mm in all directions was set for the PECs. All simulations used broadband excitations from 440 MHz to 540 MHz with perfectly matched layers placed at a distance of one-fourth of the wavelength at 499.415 MHz. The accuracy of numerical simulations was secured by setting a convergence criterion of -40 dB for the amplitude of the port signals at the end of the simulation time interval. A typical simulation consisted of about 55 million mesh cells and took about 12 hours on a customized Z8 G4 HP workstation equipped with a dual Xeon Gold 5222 processor, 96GB RAM, and one NVidia Quadro RTX 5000 GPU acceleration card.

2.3. Power Budget Analysis

The power budget analysis was conducted to identify all the loss mechanisms within the transmit array.^{34,37} This offers insights into the sources of losses and implements methods to minimise controllable losses. A snapshot of the loss mechanisms is shown in Figure 2. The input power is the total incident power at the coil plug and the reflected power represents power lost due to impedance mismatch and inter-element coupling. Reducing the coupling and achieving a good impedance match ensures that the accepted power in the coil structure is close to the input power. The power accepted in the coil structure can be subdivided into power lost due to radiation, coil component losses, and power absorbed in the biological tissue.

The optimal design of a transmit array should involve identifying all loss mechanisms to optimally utilise the available RF power in the scanner and achieve efficient transmit excitation within the SAR constraints. While coil losses caused by the intrinsic resistances in the lumped elements and conductors can be easily minimised by carefully selecting low-loss components and materials, engineering challenges still remain for reducing the reflected power and radiated power, especially at 11.7 T.

2.4. Minimisation of RF losses using Electromagnetic Simulation

The reference design included a conventional cylindrical RF shield (350-mm diameter, 300-mm length) similar to the ones used in 7T coils to reduce radiation loss.³⁸ Although this array could be well decoupled and very low reflected power could be achieved, a significant amount of the input power is radiated in the scanner bore, thereby resulting in a weak B_1^+ field

distribution in the head model. This loss in performance is due to the cut-off frequency of the conventional cylindrical shield, which is about 502 MHz in free-space and very close to the Larmor frequency of hydrogen nuclei (499.415 MHz) at 11.7 T, and this supports wave propagation. To prevent this radiation loss and hence improve the power absorbed in the sample at 11.7 T, the cut-off frequency of the local RF shield must be increased. Several techniques such as dielectric and metallic loading have been reported in the literature to alter the dispersion characteristic of a circular waveguide.³⁹ Dielectric lining could be expensive, and it can increase the overall weight of the coil. Hence, the simplest form of metallic loading in which the ends of the cylindrical shield were folded until the inner tube was implemented. We found that the folded-end shield was sufficient to minimise the radiation loss. Furthermore, the implementation of the folded-end shield has no adverse effect on the coil usability and its openness because the folded sections of the RF shield extend from the outer tube to the inner tube of the array.

All subsequent optimisations of the transmit array design were conducted with the folded-end shield in place. However, designing coils for human brain MRI at 11.7 T is unprecedented and parameters such as optimum shield diameter and shield length are yet unknown. The extent of the loop along the z-direction, the diameter of the RF shield, and the distance from the ends of the loop to the folded-end sections were varied to determine the configuration that offered the best transmit performance. For each configuration, the adjacent element overlap had to be individually adjusted to achieve robust S-parameter performance and minimise the reflected power. This is time-consuming and laborious because full 3D EM simulations had to be performed for every change in geometry.

To keep the number of simulations tractable, three loop lengths were chosen: 12 cm (array- α), 15 cm (array- β) and 16 cm (array- γ). The diameter of the RF shield was varied from 400 mm to 450 mm. A snapshot of the different coil models is shown in Figure 3. In each case, the loops were always placed at an equal distance from the folded-end sections. The length of the RF shield was varied from 240 mm to 300 mm with 20-mm increments. Altering the shield length in effect corresponds to optimizing the distance between the loops and the folded end of the shield. In addition to power budget analysis, the transmit efficiency and coverage of all configurations were compared in CP mode. Each version can be identified as follows: for example, $\alpha_{450}(280)$ represents an array with 12-cm loops, 450-mm shield diameter, and 280-mm shield length. The total number of EM simulations given all the configurations above was 24 ($3 \times 2 \times 4$).

2.5. Array Selection using Radiofrequency Pulse Design Simulations

To select the optimal array for imaging, the design optimisation included RFPD simulations. The simulated electric and magnetic field maps from CST were exported on a 5-mm isotropic grid. Given the B_1^+ maps, RFPD simulations consisted of homogenizing the flip angle on a brain mask. The RFPD simulations were performed under the following settings to mimic realistic scenarios and constraints: 0.92 dB attenuation factor in power on field maps for cable losses, 1.5 safety factor for inter-subject variability in virtual observation points (VOPs);⁴⁰⁻⁴¹ peak 10-g SAR (10 W/kg), global SAR (3.2 W/kg), maximum voltage per channel (220 V), average power per channel (6 W); brain mask; 5 and 7 k_T-points⁴² for small tip angle (10°) and inversion (180°) pulses respectively; active-set algorithm/transmit k-space trajectory optimization;⁴³⁻⁴⁴ 40 initial random seeds; 300 iterations.

The inversion pulse was 4-ms long. Durations of 0.5 ms (short) and 1 ms (long) were attempted for the small tip angle pulse to see the potential impact of SAR and power constraints. For the calculation of the constraints, a TR of 15 ms was considered for the small tip angle pulses (3D GRE sequence). For the inversion pulse, a TR of 3 s (MPRAGE) was taken into account. The flip angle normalised root mean square error (NRMSE) results were compared to select the optimal configuration for imaging.

2.6. Proof-of-Concept Coil

The best-performing coil configuration was chosen and constructed as an 8-channel transceiver array with built-in TR switches (Figure 4A). The array consisted of two concentric fiberglass tubes with inner diameters of 285 mm and 400 mm respectively. There are three rings that connect the two tubes together and stabilise the whole assembly. The folded sections of the RF shield are realised on the inner faces of the lower ring and the middle ring as shown in Figure 4A, B. The main cylindrical shield was slotted to reduce eddy currents and realised using double-sided flexible PCB (PW Circuits, United Kingdom). This was glued onto the inner surface of the outer tube (Figure 4B). A picture of the completed coil is shown in Figure 4C.

The equivalent circuit of a single element of the constructed coil is as per the schematic shown in Figure 1A. A shielded solenoid cable trap tuned to 499.415 MHz was connected between the coil input and the TR switch. Solder pads were attached to the surface of the fiberglass tube to solder the components. Each transmit element consisted of evenly distributed fixed capacitors (13x, 2.4 pF, 100C-series; American Technical Ceramics, USA) and a trimmer capacitor (1–7.5 pF, 5610-series, Johanson Manufacturing Corporation, USA). The capacitors were interconnected using 2-mm diameter silver-plated copper wire (APX, France). All bench measurements were carried out by loading the coil with a head and shoulder phantom filled with tissue equivalent solution ($\epsilon_r = 48.7$, and $\sigma = 0.65$ S/m at 500 MHz). The insertion loss of the custom-built TR switches and the 8-channel parallel transmit cable between the coil input and the coil plug was measured, and this attenuation was then incorporated in CST circuit co-simulation.

2.7. Phantom and Ex Vivo Brain Measurement

B_1^+ mapping measurements were performed at 11.7 T using the head and shoulder phantom and the selected RF coil configuration. The sequence used was the actual flip angle imaging (AFI)⁴⁵ implemented in interferometric mode.⁴⁶ Parameters were TR = 240 ms, 3.2-mm isotropic resolution, TA = 10 min 48 s per channel. Measured complex B_1^+ maps were compared with the EM simulations after additional scaling for unaccounted losses.

Finally, for additional demonstration and proof of concept, an RF pulse design was performed based on measured B_1^+ maps and parametrised with 6 k_T -points (individual pulse duration of 0.5ms) acquired on an ex-vivo human brain with a target flip angle of 5°. The RF pulse solution was inserted in a 3D GRE sequence (TR = 30 ms, 0.85-mm isotropic resolution, TE = 2.6 ms, sagittal orientation, iPAT = 2, bandwidth per pixel = 770 Hz, TA = 12 min 24 s).

3. Results

3.1. Effect of Folded-end Shield

For the reference design with a conventional cylindrical RF shield, the average decoupling between the adjacent array elements and the next-neighbouring elements were -23 dB and -

18 dB, respectively, with a maximum coupling of -17 dB. As a result, the reflected power was minimal (1%). However, only 44% of the input power was delivered to the biological tissue and a significant amount of power (18.4%) was radiated from the system (Figure 5A). This results in a weak B_1^+ field across the sample with the maximum value of 1.04 μT for 8-W input power (Figure 5B), and the energy lost due to wave propagation along the scanner bore can be seen in Figure 5C. The effect of folding the ends of the RF shield can be seen on the power budget shown in Figure 5A and on the snapshot of the decreased wave propagation along the scanner bore in Figure 5D. The radiated power was reduced to 9.2% of the input power and the field was confined within the RF shield, resulting in a stronger B_1^+ field across the sample. Note that on all the power budget plots presented in this paper, the 1.25 dB attenuation factor that was added to represent the cable and TR switch loss until the coil plug should be considered for all the power terms to be conserved.

These initial results demonstrate that folding the ends of the RF shield is already effective in reducing the radiation loss. However, it also shows that the array performance can be improved further by minimising the controllable losses. The next sections present the results of the transmit array optimisation in conjunction with the RF shield design to achieve efficient transmit excitation.

3.2. Coil Length and Shield Diameter

For the results shown in this section, the length of the RF shield is kept constant at 300 mm. Power budget analysis of four configurations consisting of 12-cm and 16-cm long loop elements and shield diameters of 400 mm and 450 mm are shown in Figure 6A. These are denoted as $\alpha_{400}(300)$, $\alpha_{450}(300)$, $\gamma_{400}(300)$, and $\gamma_{450}(300)$. Optimising the coil in conjunction with the shield reduced the radiated power to about 9%, 4%, 5%, and 1% for these four arrays, respectively. As seen in Figure 6A, the power absorbed in the tissue increases as the losses are minimised. This would result in improved sample loading and a higher B_1^+ compared to the reference array. Note that the results of β -arrays are not included for simplicity. Furthermore, its performance was found to be in between the α -arrays and γ -arrays.

Histograms of the magnitude of the B_1^+ field generated by these arrays in CP mode are shown in Figure 6B. The α -configurations exhibited larger lower tails in the histogram, representing a more inhomogeneous B_1^+ distribution. This is mainly due to the 12-cm array offering less coverage along the z-direction compared to the 16-cm array. The coefficients of variation (CV), which is a measure of the B_1^+ homogeneity in CP mode, were calculated as follows: $CV[\alpha_{400}(300)] = 41\%$, $CV[\alpha_{450}(300)] = 39\%$, $CV[\gamma_{400}(300)] = 27.1\%$, and $CV[\gamma_{450}(300)] = 27.4\%$. The CV of α -arrays in CP mode thus was significantly higher compared to the γ -designs

The α -designs achieved higher peak B_1^+ in the centre of the brain compared to the γ -designs because they excited a smaller volume while using the same input power. The values are 1.55 μT and 1.7 μT versus 1.48 μT and 1.58 μT for 8-W input power. Besides, it is worth noting that for all array configurations the larger shield (shield 2) provided less radiated power, less losses in lumped components and metallic parts, and more absorbed power in the sample. Therefore, for both designs, the peak B_1^+ was higher for the larger 450-mm folded-end RF shield.

Ultimately, from the RFPD simulations, α -configurations exhibited larger flip angle NRMSEs of the k_T -points for all three different pulses as shown in Figure 6C. As a result, the γ -configurations were chosen for further optimization.

3.3. Length of RF Shield

The final step in the optimization process was to investigate the influence of the distance between the folded ends of the RF shield and the loop conductors. Figure 7A, B show the power budget of arrays γ_{400} and γ_{450} with shield length from 240 mm to 300 mm. The radiated power was less than 5% for all arrays. Furthermore, the radiation loss was minimum for the 240-mm length shield in the case of γ_{400} and the 300-mm shield length for γ_{450} . The reduction in radiation loss consequently increased the absorbed power (Figure 7A, B).

Figure 7C, D are histograms of the magnitude of CP-like B_1^+ fields inside the brain for all γ -designs. The coefficients of variation are very similar: $CV[\gamma_{400}(240)] = 26.7\%$, $CV[\gamma_{400}(260)] = 26.7\%$, $CV[\gamma_{400}(280)] = 27.0\%$, $CV[\gamma_{400}(300)] = 27.1\%$, $CV[\gamma_{450}(240)] = 27.1\%$, $CV[\gamma_{450}(260)] = 27.4\%$, $CV[\gamma_{450}(280)] = 27.4\%$, and $CV[\gamma_{450}(300)] = 27.4\%$. To choose the most suitable array for imaging, the RFPD simulations were carried out once again. NRMSEs of the k_T -point pulses are shown in Figure 7E.

From an RF engineering point of view, the best EM performances correspond to $\gamma_{400}(240)$ and $\gamma_{450}(280)$ because they had the least radiated power as well as the most power absorbed in the head. However, based on the results of the RFPD simulations, both designs $\gamma_{400}(260)$ and $\gamma_{450}(240)$ are superior in terms of imaging as their simulated flip angle maps were slightly more homogeneous. While these two arrays could provide similar transmit performance, $\gamma_{400}(260)$ was chosen for construction because of the smaller shield diameter. A larger RF shield would offset the coil from the iso-centre when placed on the patient table. In comparison to the reference array, the design optimisation steps resulted in an improvement of 42.3% in the simulated peak B_1^+ field in the centre of the brain (from 1.04 μT to 1.48 μT) with $\gamma_{400}(260)$ (Figure 7F). Also, the loss in the discrete components as well as the loss in metal of the chosen array reduces from 9.8% to 8.6%. Two more body models were simulated to verify the robustness of the chosen design (Figure 7G). Furthermore, the CV of the chosen array reduced from 33% to 26.7%.

3.4. Coil Validation

Figure 8A, B demonstrate good agreement between the simulated and measured S-parameters of array $\gamma_{400}(260)$ when loading with a head and shoulder phantom. All channels were matched to better than -30 dB in both simulation and measurement. A higher level of decoupling was achieved in the constructed coil because the overlap between the neighbour elements was adjusted individually while all overlaps were of the same distance in the simulations. The average adjacent and next-neighbour coupling are -20.5 dB and -16.5 dB in the simulation versus -26.7 dB and -15.6 dB in the experiment, respectively.

Figure 9 compares the simulated and experimental B_1^+ field maps in the tissue-equivalent phantom while driving the coil in CP mode. Overall, there is good agreement in the spatial distribution of the B_1^+ field between simulation and measurement. Furthermore, the simulated peak B_1^+ in the centre of the phantom's head was 1.90 μT per 8-W input power at the coil plug while the measured value was 1.85 μT . Discrepancies between the simulations and the measurements yet remain in the periphery of the phantom and are believed to be due to imperfections of the S-matrix in the numerical domain. There is also good agreement in the spatial distribution pattern on the single-channel map.

Figure 10 presents the ex-vivo imaging results. The NRMSE returned from the RF pulse design over the full 3D brain mask was 8.6%. The CP mode of excitation produced an intense,

bright spot in the middle of the image as well as a ring of low signal particularly visible in the coronal orientation, due to constructive and deconstructive interferences. The use of parallel transmission here mitigates to a great extent the RF field inhomogeneity problem by flattening the excitation profile and returning a more homogeneous signal intensity image. No bias field correction, e.g. due to receive sensitivity, was performed.

4. Discussion

This work analysed the sources of losses to the power applied to a transmit array at 11.7 T, and a solution was developed to minimise the losses and maximise the power delivered to the biological tissue. A proof-of-concept transceiver array was constructed to validate the simulation results using phantom and ex-vivo scans. Preserving the available RF power is especially important at 11.7 T due to the increase in the inherent losses such as on coaxial cables and components. Furthermore, conventional RF shields act as cylindrical waveguides at 11.7 T and methods must be developed to alter their dispersion characteristics and minimise power loss due to wave propagation.

We found that folding the ends of the RF shield and subsequent optimisation steps reduced the radiated power from 1.47 W in the reference design to 0.19 W in the chosen design. The numerical simulations and experimental validations demonstrate that the folded-end sections increased the cut-off frequency and effectively prevented energy loss due to radiation. As a result, B_1^+ field distribution within the coil is improved as shown in Figure 4D. Further optimisation of the coil in conjunction with the RF shield geometry resulted in an improvement of B_1^+ efficiency of up to 42% compared to the reference design.

Duke's full sized body model and body models truncated at the level of shoulders as well as the neck were evaluated. The radiation loss was the same (0.19 W) for the full sized and the body model truncated at shoulder level. However, it increased to 0.3 W for the model truncated at the neck level. This allowed us to use body model truncated at shoulder level in this study. The computation time for the full body model was 32 hours and 30 minutes whereas the truncated model required 12 hours and 30 minutes, representing a substantial reduction in computation time. The folded end RF shield confines the EM field within the coil volume and hence the truncated body model was sufficient.

Preliminary simulations showed that the B_1^+ efficiency of an array with a 500-mm RF shield diameter is marginally higher than that of an array with a 400-mm diameter shield. However, this was not included in further optimisation because a larger RF coil poses challenges such as inability to align the coil to the isocentre in the XY-plane as well as subject's discomfort in the neck because the coil would sit high on the patient table. Based on the Principle of Reciprocity of MR signals, our result is consistent with Ref. 47, in which the maximum SNR of receive arrays was shown to monotonically increase with the shield diameter when the loops' axis is perpendicular to the shield side or there is no longitudinal component of the H-field.

Our simulations did not establish a trend between shield length, shield diameter, and radiated power (Figure 7A, B). On all array configurations considered in this work, however, it was observed that the array S-parameters were significantly altered when the folded-end sections were close (less than 4 cm) to the coil elements. Together with the findings in Ref. 47, our results emphasise the need to optimise RF shield designs in conjunction with the transmit array at UHF to achieve optimal transmit performance.

Our optimisation workflow included RFPD simulations to select the optimal configuration, including explicit SAR and power constraints. One weakness of the RFPD simulations was that B_0 field inhomogeneity was not taken into account for simplicity. The 0.5 ms small tip angle pulse, given its short duration, however, should be relatively robust versus B_0 offsets and its performance thus not much affected. The results demonstrate that the best-performing coil in conventional CP mode, in terms of peak B_1^+ in the centre, is not the preferred configuration as per the RFPD simulations. The array with the maximum peak B_1^+ in CP mode indeed does not necessarily imply the preferred configuration for imaging in terms of NRMSE. Given the many degrees of freedom in pTX, the CP mode still was chosen as a simple standard to first guide the optimizations, but one cannot rule out the existence of a more relevant transmit mode. In practice, it also remains useful to have a simple transmit mode for head localization, B_0 and B_1^+ field mapping etc. Our B_1^+ field mapping sequence for instance here was an interferometric sequence playing by default the CP mode and where transmit channels were sequentially de-phased by 180° one by one. It is thus desirable that the default-mode yields reasonable field homogeneity to avoid strong B_1^+ voids. For our particular coil architecture, the CP mode returns a relatively smooth profile and close to optimal CV in a static RF shim configuration. Interestingly also, one can observe that the NRMSEs found with RFPD appear to correlate well with the coefficient of variation of the transmit field in CP mode. As a result, this metric could potentially serve as a useful guide and surrogate for RF pulse performance. For the CP mode again, the more homogeneous profile was returned by the $\gamma_{400}(260)$ design with a CV of 26.7%, leading after RFPD of k_T -points to less than 7% and 2% NRMSEs for the small and large flip angle NRMSEs, respectively. The corresponding CV values obtained using volume birdcage coils at 3T and 7T are 13% and 22%, respectively.⁴⁸⁻
⁴⁹ While $\gamma_{400}(240)$ and $\gamma_{450}(280)$ provided the higher peak B_1^+ values, $\gamma_{400}(260)$ and $\gamma_{450}(240)$ were found to be more suitable for imaging by the RFPD simulations. This suggests in general caution when making design choices based on B_1^+ maps alone, whereby the relationship between optimized NRMSE and field maps is a non-trivial one.

Several transmit arrays for UHF MRI have been proposed, which use different array elements such as loops, dipoles, microstrips, and combinations of loops and dipoles. Although we used a conventional loop array to demonstrate and validate the workflow, design issues that are highlighted in this article will be common for the different array elements at 11.7 T. Therefore, the presented workflow is applicable to any of the array types. Future studies will consist of applying this workflow to determine the optimal element type that offers the best performance for MRI at 11.7 T.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we present a new workflow, which is especially beneficial to develop transmit arrays for ultra-high field strengths such as 11.7 T. Extensive EM simulations in combination with RFPD simulations were used to identify the suitable array configuration for imaging. An 8-channel transceiver array was fabricated to validate the numerical simulations using phantom and ex-vivo measurements. Analysis of the loss mechanisms and optimising the RF shield design in conjunction with the array design improved the transmit efficiency by 42% when compared with the reference design. Importantly, the RFPD simulations performed under realistic SAR and power constraints demonstrated that the most suitable array configuration for imaging is not the array that produced the maximum B_1^+ in CP mode, which is contrary to current practice at UHF.

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Conflict of Interest

Aurélien Massire is an employee of Siemens Healthcare SAS, Saint-Denis, France; and Shajan Gunamony is a shareholder of MR CoilTech Limited, Glasgow, UK.

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